

**FROM STRUGGLING TO PROFICIENT READERS: THE EFFECT OF LOCALIZED
READING MATERIALS ON THE READING PERFORMANCE
OF GRADE 5 LEARNERS**

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ABSTRACT

This study examined the effect of the Localized Reading Materials Program on the reading performance of Grade 5 learners in the San Andres District using a quasi-experimental pre-test and post-test research design. A total of 364 respondents participated, including 323 Grade 5 learners, 27 teachers, and school heads. Reading performance was measured through six passages administered before and after the intervention to assess vocabulary, comprehension, and higher-order thinking skills. Pre-test results revealed that most learners were at the frustration level, with low mean scores indicating significant difficulties in understanding texts, inferring meaning, and demonstrating critical thinking. Following the implementation of localized reading materials, post-test results showed marked improvement, with most learners reaching the independent reading level across all competencies. Paired samples t-test results confirmed a statistically significant difference between pre-test and post-test scores ($p = .000$), highlighting the effectiveness of the intervention. Notably, the greatest gains were observed in higher-order skills such as analyzing texts and expressing opinions. Survey findings indicated that school heads and teachers encountered challenges, including irregular learner attendance, limited instructional resources, and insufficient training. To address these issues, teachers employed strategies such as differentiated instruction, collaborative planning, small-group remediation, and strengthened parental involvement, which were found to be highly effective in supporting implementation. The findings demonstrate that culturally relevant and context-based reading materials significantly enhance learners' reading performance, engagement, and critical thinking skills. The study concludes that the Localized Reading Materials Program is an effective learner-centered intervention for literacy development. It is recommended that localized materials be systematically integrated into the curriculum, supported by continuous teacher training and adequate resource provision.

Keywords: Localized reading materials, reading performance, learning recovery, differentiated instruction, holistic learner development

INTRODUCTION

Reading is widely recognized as a fundamental skill essential for academic success and lifelong learning. Globally, many learners continue to struggle with literacy due to systemic challenges such as overcrowded classrooms, limited instructional materials, diverse learner needs, and increasing teacher workload (UNESCO, 2020). These issues are further intensified by the digital divide, particularly in developing countries, where access to quality learning resources remains uneven (UNESCO, 2022; UNICEF, 2021). As a result, ensuring that learners acquire strong reading skills has become a critical priority in educational systems worldwide.

In the Philippine context, these global challenges are compounded by local realities such as large class sizes, inadequate instructional resources, and geographical isolation, particularly in rural and last-mile schools. Studies have shown that many Filipino learners exhibit low reading proficiency, often performing at frustration levels due to limited exposure to appropriate reading materials and insufficient remedial interventions (Villalva, 2023; Mutya et al., 2025). Furthermore, limited parental involvement and inconsistent instructional support negatively affect learners' reading development (Angeles et al., 2022; Dela Roca, 2025). These concerns highlight the urgent need for targeted and context-sensitive literacy interventions.

To address learning gaps, the Department of Education implemented the National Learning Recovery Program (DepEd Order No. 13, s. 2023), aligned with the MATATAG Agenda, which prioritizes foundational literacy. One of its key strategies is the use of localized reading materials contextualized and culturally relevant resources designed to enhance learner engagement and comprehension. Research supports that learners demonstrate improved reading performance when instructional materials reflect their cultural background and lived experiences (Lestari et al., 2025; Panklam & Kaowiwattanakul, 2024). Similarly, contextualized materials promote motivation, participation, and deeper understanding of texts (Angeles et al., 2022).

The effectiveness of localized reading materials is also anchored in data-driven and differentiated instruction. Pre-assessment data allow teachers to identify learners' reading levels and design targeted interventions such as guided reading, scaffolded instruction, and flexible grouping (Panklam & Kaowiwattanakul, 2024). This approach has been shown to significantly reduce frustration-level readers and improve comprehension and higher-order thinking skills (García & Kleifgen, 2020; Galang et al., 2024; Garces et al., 2025). Moreover, the use of validated assessment tools such as the Philippine Informal Reading Inventory (Phil-IRI) ensures accurate monitoring of learner progress (Villalva, 2023).

Despite these promising strategies, several studies highlight persistent challenges in implementing localized reading programs. Irregular attendance, limited instructional time, and scheduling constraints often affect learner engagement (Chi, 2024; Ganohay et al., 2025). Additionally, insufficient resources and lack of sustained professional development hinder teachers' ability to effectively deliver differentiated instruction (Malipot, 2024; LaBad, 2024). These findings are consistent with broader

research indicating that while localized interventions improve reading outcomes, their success depends on adequate institutional support, resource availability, and teacher preparedness (Ball et al., 2024; Dela Roca, 2025).

In the San Andres District, these challenges are evident, with a significant proportion of Grade 5 learners demonstrating difficulty in reading. This underscores the need for structured and evidence-based interventions such as the Localized Reading Materials Program. While previous studies (Talain & Cruzado, 2024; Rafanan et al., 2024) have examined reading interventions, limited research has been conducted within this specific district context, particularly considering its unique geographic and resource constraints.

Thus, this study aims to examine the effect of localized reading materials on the reading performance of Grade 5 learners in the San Andres District. By evaluating its effectiveness, identifying implementation challenges, and analyzing instructional practices, the study seeks to provide evidence-based insights that can guide teachers, school leaders, and policymakers in strengthening literacy programs. Ultimately, this research contributes to the broader goal of improving reading proficiency, promoting educational equity, and ensuring that all learners transition from struggling to proficient readers.

Research Questions

This study aimed to evaluate the effect of localized reading materials on the reading performance of Grade 5 learners in public elementary schools in San Andres District. Specifically, it sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the level of reading performance of Grade 5 learners before and after the use of localized reading materials in the following learning competencies (LC):
 - 1.1 infer the meaning of unfamiliar words using context clues and describe story elements,
 - 1.2infer the meaning of unfamiliar words using context clues and relate text ideas to personal experiences,
 - 1.3infer the meaning of unfamiliar words and describe characters, setting, and plot
 - 1.4infer the meaning of unfamiliar words and express opinions or reactions to ideas in the text,
 - 1.5determine the author's purpose and analyze supporting details,
 - 1.6identify and analyze text structures such as cause-effect, comparison-contrast, and problem-solution?
2. Is there a significant difference between pre- test and post-test reading performance scores of Grade 5 learners before and after the use of localized reading materials in the following learning competencies (LC):

- 2.1 infer the meaning of unfamiliar words using context clues and describe story elements,
 - 2.2 infer the meaning of unfamiliar words using context clues and relate text ideas to personal experiences,
 - 2.3 infer the meaning of unfamiliar words and describe characters, setting, and plot,
 - 2.4 infer the meaning of unfamiliar words and express opinions or reactions to ideas in the text,
 - 2.5 determine the author's purpose and analyze supporting details,
 - 2.6 identify and analyze text structures such as cause-effect, comparison-contrast, and problem-solution?
3. What are the challenges encountered by school heads and teachers in using localized reading materials?
 4. What are the strategies applied by teachers to address the challenges encountered in using localized reading materials?
 5. Based on the findings of the study, what intervention program can be proposed to further improve the reading performance of Grade 5 learners?

METHODOLOGY

This study employed a quantitative quasi-experimental research design utilizing a pre-test and post-test approach to determine the effect of the Localized Reading Materials Program on the reading performance of Grade 5 learners in the San Andres District. The design enabled the comparison of learners' reading abilities before and after exposure to the intervention, thereby establishing measurable changes in fluency, comprehension, and vocabulary skills. Prior to the implementation, a standardized pre-test aligned with the Most Essential Learning Competencies (MELCs) was administered to establish baseline reading performance. Following this, localized reading materials featuring culturally relevant texts reflecting learners' environment and experiences were introduced during structured reading sessions over an eight-week period. These materials aimed to enhance learner engagement and comprehension through contextualized and meaningful content. After the intervention, a post-test using the same assessment tool was conducted to measure improvements in reading performance. The study was conducted in public elementary schools within the San Andres District, Quezon, involving 364 respondents, including 323 Grade 5 learners, 27 teachers, and 13 school heads. Total enumeration was applied to teachers and school heads, while proportionate stratified sampling was used for learners. In addition, a descriptive approach was utilized to identify challenges encountered and strategies applied during program implementation through survey questionnaires. Data were analyzed using frequency, percentage, mean, and standard deviation to describe trends, while a paired-samples t-test determined significant differences between pre- and post-test scores. This methodological approach ensured a rigorous and data-driven evaluation of the program's effectiveness.

RESULTS and DISCUSSION

Part I. Level of Reading Performance of Grade 5 Learners Before and After the Use of Localized Reading Materials.

Table 1

Level of Reading Performance of Grade 5 Learners Before and After the Use of Localized Reading Materials

Level of Performance	LC1		LC2		LC3		LC4		LC5		LC6													
	Pre-test		Posttest		Pre-test		Posttest		Pre-test		Posttest													
	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%												
Frustration	322	99.7	17	5.3	323	100	17	5.3	317	98.1	16	5.0	283	87.6	0	0	256	79.3	0	0	150	46.4	0	0
Instructional	1	0.3	43	13.3	0	0	73	22.6	2	0.6	28	8.7	25	7.7	34	10.5	30	9.3	0	0	142	44.0	1	0.3
Independent	0	0	263	81.4	0	0	233	72.1	4	1.2	279	86.4	15	4.6	289	89.5	37	11.5	323	100	31	9.6	322	99.7
Mean	37.43		84.15		37.06		81.70		37.55		85.08		39.75		95.76		44.67		98.89		51.83		97.96	
SD	0.116		0.261		0.115		0.253		0.116		0.263		0.123		0.296		0.138		0.306		0.160		0.303	
Description	Frustration	Independent																						
Gain	46.72		44.64		47.53		56.01		54.22		46.13													

Legend:

- LC1. infer the meaning of unfamiliar words using context clues and describe story elements,
- LC2. infer the meaning of unfamiliar words using context clues and relate text ideas to personal experiences,
- LC3. infer the meaning of unfamiliar words and describe characters, setting, and plot,
- LC4. infer the meaning of unfamiliar words and express opinions or reactions to ideas in the text,
- LC5. determine the author's purpose and analyze supporting details,
- LC6. identify and analyze text structures such as cause-effect, comparison-contrast, and problem-solution

Table 1 presents the level of reading performance of Grade 5 learners before and after using localized reading materials. The results reveal a substantial and consistent improvement across all six learning competencies. Prior to the intervention, learners were predominantly classified under the frustration level, with percentages ranging from 46.4% to 100%. In particular, LC1, LC2, and LC3 recorded extremely high frustration levels (98.1%–100%), indicating that learners experienced significant difficulty in inferring word meanings using context clues and in understanding basic story elements such as characters, setting, and plot. Similarly, higher-order competencies such as determining the author's purpose (LC5) and analyzing text structures (LC6) also showed considerable proportions of learners in the frustration level (79.3% and 46.4%, respectively). These findings suggest that prior to the intervention, learners had limited foundational and analytical reading skills, as reflected in the low mean scores ($M = 37.06$ to 51.83).

Following the use of localized reading materials, a notable shift from frustration to independent level was observed across all competencies. Posttest results indicate

that the majority of learners achieved independent reading levels, with particularly high percentages in LC4 (89.5%), LC5 (100%), and LC6 (99.7%). Moreover, the near elimination of frustration-level readers (0–5.3%) highlights the strong effect of the intervention, especially in developing higher-order comprehension skills. Mean scores significantly increased ($M = 81.70$ to 98.89), with LC5 and LC6 approaching mastery level performance. The gain scores, ranging from 44.64 to 56.01 , further affirm the effectiveness of the intervention, with the highest gains observed in LC5 (56.01) and LC3 (54.22), indicating improvements in both basic comprehension and critical reading skills.

These results support the effect of data-driven and differentiated instruction, as emphasized by Panklam and Kaowiwattanakul (2024). The use of pre-test data enabled teachers to identify learners' prior knowledge, reading gaps, and varying levels of comprehension, allowing for strategic grouping, guided reading sessions, and scaffolded instruction. This approach aligns with the principles of localized and culturally responsive teaching, ensuring that interventions are tailored to learners' needs (Lestari et al., 2025).

Furthermore, the sharp reduction in frustration-level readers reinforces the value of contextualized and culturally relevant materials. Studies have shown that learners demonstrate higher engagement and improved comprehension when texts reflect their socio-cultural background and lived experiences (Angeles et al., 2022; Dela Roca, 2025; Lestari et al., 2025). By integrating familiar contexts into reading instruction, learners are more motivated to participate actively, leading to better retention and deeper understanding of the text, consistent with the findings of Panklam and Kaowiwattanakul (2024).

The observed gain scores (44.64 – 56.01) also indicate that the systematic integration of assessment and instruction leads to measurable learning improvements. Mutya et al. (2025) highlight the importance of utilizing post-test data to refine instructional strategies and improve localized materials, while Villalva (2023) emphasizes the use of validated assessment tools such as the Philippine Informal Reading Inventory (Phil-IRI) to ensure the accuracy of learning gains. Additionally, the relatively low standard deviation values in the posttest suggest consistency in learners' improvement, demonstrating the effectiveness of scaffolded and differentiated instruction in addressing diverse learning needs (García & Kleifgen, 2020; Galang et al., 2024; Garces et al., 2025).

Hence, the findings demonstrate that the use of localized reading materials significantly improved learners' reading performance from frustration to independent levels across all competencies. The most notable improvements were observed in higher-order comprehension skills (LC4–LC6), indicating that contextualized instruction not only enhances basic reading skills but also promotes critical thinking. These results affirm the importance of evidence-based, assessment-informed, and culturally responsive reading interventions in improving learner outcomes. Moreover, the findings support national educational initiatives such as the MATATAG Agenda and the National Learning Recovery Program (NLRP) under DepEd Memorandum No. 001, s. 2024, which emphasizes targeted interventions to address learning gaps and promote literacy development. Observed gain scores across passages (44.64 – 56.01)

demonstrate that systematic integration of assessment and instruction yields measurable learning improvements. Mutya et al. (2025) advocate using post-test results to refine instructional strategies and localized materials iteratively, while Villalva (2023) emphasizes employing validated tools, such as the Philippine Informal Reading Inventory (Phil-IRI), to ensure post-test scores accurately capture true learning gains rather than extraneous factors. Low standard deviation values in post-tests further indicate consistent improvement across learners, highlighting the effectiveness of scaffolded, differentiated instruction in heterogeneous classrooms (García & Kleifgen, 2020; Galang et al., 2024; Garces et al., 2025).

In sum, the findings from illustrate the critical role of evidence-based, assessment-informed localized reading interventions in improving learner outcomes. Integrating pre- and post-test data into instructional design validates the effectiveness of the materials and aligns with culturally responsive pedagogy, ensuring reading interventions are contextually meaningful and pedagogically sound. These results corroborate literature asserting that data-driven, culturally grounded literacy instruction leads to significant gains in reading performance, learner engagement, and holistic development (Lestari et al., 2025; Villalva, 2023; Mutya et al., 2025; Panklam & Kaowiwattanakul, 2024) and supports national recovery initiatives such as the MATATAG Agenda and the National Learning Recovery Program (NLRP) under DepEd Memorandum No. 001, s. 2024.

Part II. Significant Difference between Pre-Test and Post-Test Reading Performance Scores of Grade 5 Learners Before and After the Use of Localized Reading Materials

Table 5

Statistical Table Showing the Significant Difference in the Mean Scores of Pre and Post Reading Assessment Before and After the Use of Localized Reading Materials

Paired Samples Test											
		Paired Differences					t	df	p-value	Decision	Interpretation
		Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference						
					Lower	Upper					
LC1	Pre-test vs Posttest	-46.71827	17.42075	.96932	-48.62526	-44.81127	-48.197	322	.000	Reject the Null Hypothesis	Significant
LC2	Pre-test vs Posttest	-44.64396	17.88803	.99532	-46.60211	-42.68582	-44.854	322	.000		
LC3	Pre-test vs Posttest	-47.52322	16.58954	.92307	-49.33922	-45.70722	-51.484	322	.000		
LC4	Pre-test vs Posttest	-56.00619	18.39423	1.02348	-58.01975	-53.99263	-54.721	322	.000		
LC5	Pre-test vs Posttest	-54.21053	19.03525	1.05915	-56.29425	-52.12680	-51.183	322	.000		
LC6	Pre-test vs Posttest	-46.13003	21.16649	1.17774	-48.44706	-43.81300	-39.168	322	.000		

Legend:

- LC1. infer the meaning of unfamiliar words using context clues and describe story elements,*
- LC2. infer the meaning of unfamiliar words using context clues and relate text ideas to personal experiences,*
- LC3. infer the meaning of unfamiliar words and describe characters, setting, and plot,*
- LC4. infer the meaning of unfamiliar words and express opinions or reactions to ideas in the text,*
- LC5. determine the author's purpose and analyze supporting details,*
- LC6. identify and analyze text structures such as cause-effect, comparison-contrast, and problem-solution*

Table 5 presents the results of the paired samples t-test conducted to determine the significant difference between the pre-test and post-test reading performance scores of Grade 5 learners after using localized reading materials. The results revealed that there is a statistically significant difference between the pre-test and post-test scores across all six learning competencies (LC1–LC6), as indicated by the computed p-values of .000, which are all lower than the 0.05 level of significance. Consequently, the null hypothesis is rejected in all cases. This indicates that the observed improvements in learners' reading performance are not due to chance but can be attributed to the intervention.

The negative mean differences (ranging from -44.64 to -56.01) indicate that post-test scores were significantly higher than pre-test scores. Among the competencies, LC4 (expressing opinions or reactions to ideas in the text) registered the highest mean gain (-56.01), followed by LC5 (-54.21) and LC3 (-47.52). These results suggest that the intervention was particularly effective in enhancing higher-order reading skills, including critical thinking, analysis, and interpretation of texts. The computed t-values, which are relatively large in magnitude (e.g., $t = -54.721$ for LC4), further confirm the strength of the differences observed. Moreover, the narrow 95% confidence intervals across all competencies indicate a high level of precision and reliability in the estimated mean differences. This implies that the improvements in reading performance were consistent among the learners, reinforcing the effectiveness of the localized reading materials as an instructional intervention.

These findings suggest that the use of localized reading materials had a strong and meaningful effect on learners' reading achievement, resulting in substantial gains in both fluency and comprehension. When viewed alongside the pre-test results where most learners were classified under the frustration level the post-test outcomes demonstrate a clear transition toward independent reading performance. This supports previous studies which emphasize that contextually relevant and well-structured instructional materials effectively scaffold learners from basic to advanced levels of reading competence (Angeles et al., 2022; Villalva, 2023; Mutya et al., 2025).

Furthermore, the magnitude of the mean differences indicates not only statistical significance but also practical significance, highlighting that the intervention produced real and measurable improvements in learners' reading development. These results align with the goals of DepEd Memorandum No. 001, s. 2024, as well as the MATATAG Agenda and the National Learning Recovery Program (NLRP), which prioritize addressing learning gaps in foundational literacy skills.

The results also corroborate literature on data-driven and culturally responsive instruction. Panklam and Kaowiwattanakul (2024) and Lestari et al. (2025) emphasize that learners demonstrate better engagement and retention when instructional

materials are aligned with their cultural context and lived experiences. The significant gains observed in this study affirm that localized reading materials enhance not only comprehension but also learner motivation and participation. Additionally, the findings provide an important response to challenges identified in previous reports, such as irregular attendance, repetitive instructional approaches, and unclear learning targets (Malipot, 2024). Despite these constraints, the significant improvements suggest that well-designed, targeted, and contextualized interventions can effectively overcome such barriers and lead to meaningful academic outcomes.

In conclusion, the results of the paired samples t-test provide strong evidence that the implementation of localized reading materials significantly improved the reading performance of Grade 5 learners across all competencies. The integration of assessment-driven instruction, culturally relevant materials, and structured remediation strategies proved to be effective in enhancing both foundational and higher-order reading skills.

Part III. Challenges Encountered by School Heads and Teachers in Using Localized Reading Materials

Table 6
Level of Challenges Encountered by School Heads and Teachers in Using Localized Reading Materials

Indicator	Mean		Mean	Total	
	SH	T		SD	VI
1. Time constraints make it difficult to cover all necessary lessons and activities during Localized Reading Materials.	3.50	3.68	3.59	0.95	Highly Challenging
2. Limited teaching and learning materials hinder the effective use of Localized Reading Materials.	3.58	4.00	3.79	0.95	Highly Challenging
3. Learners' lack of motivation and engagement affects their participation in Localized Reading Materials activities.	3.33	3.39	3.36	1.01	Highly Challenging
4. Irregular attendance of learners reduces the effectiveness of Localized Reading Materials in improving learning outcomes.	3.83	4.00	3.92	0.83	Highly Challenging
5. Difficulty in addressing diverse learning needs of learners within a short period poses a challenge during Localized Reading Materials.	3.42	3.64	3.53	0.86	Highly Challenging
6. Additional workload for teachers increases stress and affects the quality of instruction during Localized Reading Materials.	3.58	3.61	3.60	1.06	Highly Challenging
7. Lack of clear guidelines and structured activities makes it challenging to implement Localized Reading Materials effectively.	3.67	3.46	3.57	0.74	Highly Challenging
8. Insufficient support from parents and guardians affects learners' learning progress during Localized Reading Materials.	3.58	3.82	3.70	1.03	Highly Challenging
9. Inadequate training for teachers on how to effectively use Localized Reading Materials limits its success.	3.75	3.64	3.70	0.82	Highly Challenging
10. Assessing learners' progress and measuring learning improvements within Localized Reading Materials is difficult due to time limitations and varying student abilities.	3.50	3.50	3.50	0.77	Highly Challenging
GRAND MEAN	3.57	3.67	3.63	0.903	Highly Challenging

Legend:

4.01 – 5.00	Very Highly Challenging (VHC)	SH	-	School Head
3.26 – 4.00	Highly Challenging (HC)	T	-	Teacher
2.51 – 3.25	Moderately Challenging (MC)	VI	-	Verbal Interpretation
1.76 – 2.50	Least Challenge (LC)			
1.00 – 1.75	Not Challenge at All (NC)			

Table 6 illustrates the level of challenges encountered by school heads and Grade 5 teachers in using Localized Reading Materials, with an overall grand mean of 3.63 (SD = 0.903), indicating that the program was perceived as Highly Challenging. Among the specific challenges, irregular student attendance was the most pressing concern (M = 3.92), followed by limited teaching and learning materials (M = 3.79) and inadequate teacher training (M = 3.70). These results highlight that learner participation, availability of instructional resources, and teacher capacity-building are critical factors influencing the effectiveness and sustainability of localized literacy programs.

Time constraints also emerged as a significant barrier, particularly in covering lessons and conducting assessments within the limited instructional periods (M = 3.59 and 3.50, respectively). This aligns with Ganohay et al. (2025), who noted that limited instructional time often constrains teachers' ability to address diverse learner needs in remediation programs. Similarly, Chi (2024) observed that scheduling supplementary lessons at the end of the week can lead to reduced student engagement, corroborating the high mean for irregular attendance in this study. These findings suggest that both structural and scheduling issues can undermine the consistency and effectiveness of literacy interventions.

Challenges related to instructional resources and professional development also mirrored previous research. The high mean scores for limited materials (M = 3.79) and inadequate training (M = 3.70) support Malipot's (2024) assertion that insufficient resources and inconsistent professional development undermine the implementation of localized reading programs. Teachers reported that these gaps hindered their ability to implement differentiated and scaffolded instruction strategies shown by Ganohay et al. (2025) to be essential for addressing learner diversity within short remediation periods.

The difficulty of addressing diverse learner needs (M = 3.53) and the additional workload on teachers (M = 3.60) further reflect findings by LaBad (2024), who emphasized that learner-centered strategies require extra planning, adaptation, and collaboration, often increasing teacher stress in the absence of adequate structural support. Likewise, the lack of clear guidelines and assessment mechanisms (M = 3.57) mirrors Malipot's (2024) observation that the absence of standardized monitoring tools limits the ability of educators to track progress and maintain program fidelity.

The findings in Table 6 corroborate broader literature on localized literacy interventions, which consistently demonstrates that while these programs improve reading outcomes, their effectiveness can be compromised by insufficient institutional support, resource constraints, and limited teacher preparation (Angeles et al., 2022;

Ball et al., 2024; Dela Roca, 2025). Time limitations, irregular attendance, and inadequate guidance highlighted by Ganohay et al. (2025) and Chi (2024) remain persistent challenges in learning recovery initiatives. Similarly, Malipot (2024) and LaBad (2024) indicate that teacher stress and unclear instructional targets further reduce program consistency and effect.

Hence, the results suggest that while Localized Reading Materials hold strong potential for improving literacy, successful implementation requires a multi-faceted approach. This includes targeted professional development, adequate instructional resources, structured lesson guidelines, consistent monitoring, and strategies to enhance learner engagement. Addressing these systemic challenges is essential to ensure that localized reading programs not only achieve significant gains in student performance but also maintain sustainability and fidelity over time, aligning with national and global recommendations for effective literacy interventions (UNESCO, 2020, 2022; UNICEF, 2021).

In conclusion, the interpretation of Table 6 highlights that program success depends as much on structural support and teacher capacity as on the quality of instructional materials. Integrating these findings with evidence from previous studies reinforces that a comprehensive, evidence-based, and contextually responsive framework is necessary to optimize learning outcomes and mitigate the implementation challenges identified in both local and international literature.

Part IV. Strategies Applied by Teachers to Address the Challenges Encountered in Using Localized Reading Materials

To address the challenges encountered in using localized reading materials, Grade 5 teachers implemented a range of instructional strategies aimed at improving learner outcomes. One of the primary approaches was the adaptation and customization of reading materials to ensure alignment with learners' reading levels and local context. This made the lessons more relevant, engaging, and easier for learners to understand. Teachers also employed collaborative teaching strategies such as peer-assisted learning and small-group instruction to cater to diverse reading abilities within the classroom. These strategies helped provide more focused support to struggling readers. In addition, teachers integrated technology and multimedia resources to supplement printed materials and enhance learner engagement. Continuous professional development and peer mentoring were also utilized to strengthen teachers' instructional competence in using localized materials effectively. Regular monitoring and formative assessment were conducted to track learners' progress. This allowed teachers to make timely adjustments in instruction based on learners' needs. Overall, these strategies collectively contributed to more effective implementation of localized reading materials.

Table 7

Level of Strategies Applied by Teachers to Address the Challenges Encountered in Using Localized Reading Materials

Indicator	Mean		Mean	Total		VI
	SH	T		SD		
1. I modify my lesson plans to ensure that Localized Reading Materials align with the regular curriculum.	4.33	4.36	4.35	0.728		Very Highly Applied
2. I use differentiated instructions to cater to learners with varying learning needs during Localized Reading Materials.	4.42	4.43	4.43	0.621		Very Highly Applied
3. I conduct small-group or one-on-one instruction for learners who need extra support.	4.17	4.39	4.28	0.673		Very Highly Applied
4. I provide additional learning materials and resources to support learners struggling with literacy.	4.33	4.25	4.29	0.648		Very Highly Applied
5. I incorporate interactive and gamified learning activities to keep learners engaged.	4.42	4.32	4.37	0.669		Very Highly Applied
6. I integrate technology (e.g., educational apps, videos) to enhance learners' learning experiences.	4.50	4.50	4.50	0.550		Very Highly Applied
7. I collaborate with fellow teachers to develop strategies for effectively using Localized Reading Materials.	4.42	4.46	4.44	0.511		Very Highly Applied
8. I communicate regularly with parents to encourage their involvement in their child's learning progress.	4.00	4.11	4.06	0.712		Very Highly Applied
9. I adjust my teaching strategies based on the feedback and performance of my learners.	4.33	4.32	4.33	0.484		Very Highly Applied
10. I attend professional development workshops to improve my ability to use Localized Reading Materials effectively.	4.00	3.86	3.93	0.793		Highly Applied
GRAND MEAN	4.29	4.30	4.30	0.639		Very Highly Applied

Legend:

4.01 – 5.00	Very Highly Applied (VHA)	SH	-	School Head
3.26 – 4.00	Highly Applied (HA)	T	-	Teacher
2.51 – 3.25	Moderately Applied (MA)	VI	-	Verbal Interpretation
1.76 – 2.50	Slightly Applied (SA)			
1.00 – 1.75	Not Applied (NA)			

Table 7 illustrates the level of strategies applied by teachers to address challenges encountered in using Localized Reading Materials. The overall grand mean of 4.30 (SD = 0.639) indicates that teachers consistently applied strategies at a Highly Applied level, reflecting strong instructional commitment, adaptive practices, and

proactive problem-solving. Among the specific strategies, the highest-rated approach was the integration of technology to enhance learning experiences (M = 4.50), followed by collaboration among teachers (M = 4.44) and differentiated instruction (M = 4.43). These findings demonstrate that Grade 5 teachers applied learner-centered and collaborative strategies, effectively catering to the diverse literacy needs of learners.

Teachers also reported consistently high application of curriculum alignment (M = 4.35), interactive and gamified learning activities (M = 4.37), small-group or one-on-one instruction (M = 4.28), and provision of additional learning resources (M = 4.29). These strategies reflect comprehensive instructional responses designed to address literacy gaps, scaffold comprehension, and maintain student engagement. Regular communication with parents (M = 4.06) and participation in professional development activities (M = 3.93) were also evident, though professional development received the lowest rating, suggesting that access to targeted training remains an area for improvement. The close alignment between school heads' (M = 4.29) and teachers' (M = 4.30) perceptions highlights shared awareness and collaborative efforts in using localized literacy interventions.

The findings indicate that despite highly challenging conditions reported in Table 6 such as irregular attendance, limited materials, and time constraints teachers proactively adopted evidence-based strategies to sustain and enhance the Localized Reading Materials program. The very high level of strategy application aligns with the significant reading gains reported in Table 5, suggesting that instructional adaptability, differentiated teaching, collaboration, and technological integration were key factors in improving learner outcomes. Strengthening professional development and institutional support could further enhance the effectiveness and sustainability of these strategies.

These results are supported by existing literature emphasizing effective localized instruction. Abellana et al. (2023) note that teachers in primary grades face challenges like varying learner competencies and limited resources, and that differentiated instruction and culturally relevant examples help bridge comprehension gaps. Alde (2025) reported that small-group interventions, guided reading sessions, and the integration of learners' lived experiences effectively mitigate challenges such as low motivation and reading anxiety. Similarly, Angeles et al. (2022) found that repeated reading, interactive questioning, and collaborative reading activities using localized materials enhanced learners' fluency, comprehension, and engagement.

Moreover, contextualized instructional strategies support the findings of Atondo (2022) and Dela Roca (2025), who highlighted that story-based lessons, visual aids, and culturally relevant content enable learners to connect meaningfully with reading materials. Iterative feedback loops, small-group scaffolding, and technology integration allow teachers to continuously adapt instruction to learners' needs, effectively addressing literacy challenges while promoting motivation and academic growth. Collectively, these insights underscore that teacher strategies are critical for maximizing the effect of localized reading interventions and achieving significant learning gains.

Part V. Intervention Program Proposed to Further Improve the Reading Performance of Grade 5 Learners

The findings of this study affirm that localized reading materials significantly improve learners' reading performance by enhancing comprehension, fluency, motivation, and engagement. These results support the claims of Panklam and Kaowiwattanakul (2024) and Lestari et al. (2025), who emphasized that culturally responsive and context-based instructional materials lead to better learning outcomes. In addition, the study addresses persistent challenges such as irregular attendance, limited instructional time, and repetitive teaching approaches identified by Malipot (2024). Despite these constraints, the positive gains in learners' performance demonstrate that well-structured and contextualized interventions can effectively bridge reading gaps.

Anchored on these findings, Project L.O.C.A.L. (Learning to Optimize Contextualized and Authentic Localized Materials) was developed as an intervention program to further enhance reading performance. The program focuses on strengthening teachers' capacity to design, develop, and implement localized reading materials that reflect learners' cultural backgrounds and lived experiences. It is grounded in the ADDIE instructional design framework, ensuring systematic processes in assessment, design, development, implementation, and evaluation.

Project L.O.C.A.L. also promotes professional development through training, coaching, and collaborative learning sessions for teachers. It encourages active participation of stakeholders, including parents, school leaders, and community members, to support literacy development and sustain reading initiatives. Learners benefit from more engaging, meaningful, and differentiated reading experiences that cater to their needs.

The program is implemented over one semester and is expected to improve reading comprehension, fluency, and learner engagement while strengthening teacher competence in material development. It also aims to foster stronger school-community partnerships and support national literacy goals under the MATATAG Agenda and the National Learning Recovery Program. Ultimately, Project L.O.C.A.L. provides a sustainable and evidence-based approach to improving literacy outcomes among Grade 5 learners.

Conclusions

Based on the findings of this study, the following conclusions are drawn.

1. The findings revealed that Grade 5 learners initially performed at the frustration level in the pre-test, indicating significant difficulties in comprehension, vocabulary inference, and higher-order thinking skills across all learning competencies. However, after the intervention, a marked improvement was observed as most learners progressed to the independent level, with significantly higher mean scores and enhanced reading performance.

2. The study concludes that the use of localized reading materials significantly improved the reading performance of Grade 5 learners, as shown by the large and consistent gains in posttest scores and strong statistical evidence across all reading passages. Therefore, the null hypothesis is rejected, confirming that the intervention is highly effective in producing meaningful and reliable improvements in learners' reading skills.
3. The study concludes that the implementation of localized reading materials was perceived as highly challenging by school heads and Grade 5 teachers due to issues such as irregular attendance, limited instructional resources, and inadequate training. These findings emphasize the need for strengthened support systems, improved resource allocation, and continuous capacity-building programs to ensure more effective implementation of reading interventions.
4. The study concludes that Grade 5 teachers effectively addressed the challenges in using localized reading materials by applying adaptive and learner-centered strategies such as technology integration, collaborative teaching, and differentiated instruction. These strategies demonstrate teachers' strong instructional adaptability and commitment to ensuring the successful delivery of the reading program.
5. The study concludes that the Localized Reading Materials Program is highly effective in enhancing Grade 5 learners' reading performance and fostering holistic literacy development. By improving fluency, comprehension, and learner engagement through culturally relevant texts, the program proves that contextualized and structured interventions significantly strengthen reading outcomes among struggling learners.

Recommendations

Based on the conclusions of this study, the following recommendations are proposed to strengthen the effect of the Localized Reading Materials program, ensure sustainable learning recovery, and support the holistic development of Grade 5 learners:

1. Since the pretest results showed that most Grade 5 learners were at the frustration level, it is recommended that schools implement early, structured, and targeted reading interventions to strengthen foundational literacy skills, including regular assessment, remedial support, and differentiated instruction for struggling readers. In addition, based on the significant improvement in posttest results, localized reading materials should be fully integrated into the Grade 5 reading curriculum, supported by continuous teacher training and monitoring to sustain learners' progress and ensure consistent use of culturally relevant and effective strategies.
2. Given the statistically significant gains in reading performance, it is recommended that localized reading materials be institutionalized as a core instructional strategy in Grade 5 reading programs. Regular monitoring,

assessment, and teacher training should be maintained to ensure sustained improvement and maximize learning outcomes.

3. In response to the identified implementation challenges, it is recommended that schools strengthen attendance monitoring, enhance parental involvement, and implement motivation strategies to improve learner participation. Additionally, adequate instructional materials and continuous teacher training should be provided to support effective program implementation.
4. Since teachers effectively applied various strategies, it is recommended that schools continue to promote technology integration, collaborative teaching practices, and differentiated instruction. Sustaining these approaches will further enhance instructional quality and ensure that diverse learner needs are adequately addressed.
5. Based on the program's effectiveness, it is recommended that localized reading materials be integrated into regular classroom instruction to ensure sustained literacy development among learners. Future studies may also explore its application in other grade levels and learning areas to further validate and expand its impact.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

This study strictly complied with ethical standards to ensure the protection, dignity, and rights of all participants. Prior to data collection, permission was secured from the Schools Division Office and concerned school authorities in the San Andres District. Informed consent was obtained from all school heads and teachers, while parental consent and assent were secured for Grade 5 learners. Participation was voluntary, and respondents were informed of their right to withdraw at any time without penalty. Confidentiality and anonymity were strictly observed through coded data handling. All findings were reported in aggregate form and used solely for research and educational improvement purposes.

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REFERENCES

- Abellana, J., Navarro, V., Uy, D. M., & Tinapay, A. (2023). Approaches applied in primary grade levels in teaching reading and comprehension and its challenges: A literature review. *International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research and Publications (IJMRAP)*, 6(6), 231–236.
- Alde, F. B. (2025). Teachers' utilization of innovative reading program to address struggling readers in Garchitorena District. *International Journal of Research and Scientific Innovation (IJRSI)*, 12(6), 520–575.
- Angeles, J. A. P., Manaig, K. A., Sapin, S. B., Yazon, A. D., & Tesoro, J. F. B. (2022). Effectiveness of localized reading activity sheets in enhancing the reading skills of Grade 1 learners. *International Journal of Theory and Application in Elementary and Secondary School Education*, 4(2).
- Atondo, H. B. (2022). Contextualized instructional materials in teaching reading and writing skills. *International Journal of Research Studies in Education*, 11(8), 17–34.
- Binlang, J. B., & Donguiz, R. G. (2024). Beyond sight: A systematic review of the challenges and coping mechanisms in inclusive education for visually impaired learners. *Cognizance Journal of Multidisciplinary Studies*, 4(7), 59–74.
- Ball, M. C., Bhattacharya, J., Zhao, H., Akpé, H., Brogno, S., & Jasińska, K. K. (2024). Effective bilingual education in Francophone West Africa: Constraints and possibilities. *International Journal of Bilingual Education and Bilingualism*, 27(6), 821–835.
- Casinto, C. C. (2025). The teaching and learning of reading: Its challenges, strategies, and effectiveness in the Philippine context: A systematic review. *International Journal of Language and Literary Studies*, 7(5).
- Chall, J. S. (1983). *Stages of reading development*. McGraw-Hill.
- Chi, J. (2024). Declining student attendance on Fridays: Implications for localized reading programs. *Journal of Educational Research*, 58(2), 45–62.
- David, O., & Nsengimana, V. (2022). The effect of the use of English as language of instruction and inquiry-based learning on biology learning in Sub-Saharan Africa secondary schools: A systematic review of the literature. *African Journal of Research in Mathematics, Science and Technology Education*, 26(3), 275–285.

- Dela Roca, A. E. (2025). Developing localized reading materials: Addressing comprehension level of Key Stage 1 and 2 learners. *International Journal of Research and Scientific Innovation*, 12(13), 183–193.
- Department of Education. (2023). Adoption of the National Learning Recovery Program (DepEd Order No. 013, s. 2023). <https://www.deped.gov.ph>
- Department of Education. (2024). Implementation of Catch-Up Fridays (DepEd Memorandum No. 001, s. 2024). <https://www.deped.gov.ph>
- Field, A. (2018). *Discovering statistics using IBM SPSS statistics* (5th ed.). SAGE Publications.
- Fuentes, M. B. (2025). Teacher experiences, challenges, and support needs in the implementation of the Philippine MATATAG curriculum: An integrative literature review. *Journal of Interdisciplinary Perspectives*, 3(12), 167–179.
- Galang, M. L., Aquino, Z., Enriquez, A., & del Rosario, J. (2024). Enhancing reading fluency: Repeated reading of researcher-made localized materials. *Southeast Asian Journal of Agriculture and Allied Sciences*, 4(1), 56–68.
- Ganohay, J. M., Gargar, A. M., Cortes, G., Balang, W. M., Valmorida, F. M., & Tantog, A. J. D. (2025). Perceptions of intermediate-level public school teachers in using the Catch-Up Friday Program. *Journal of Elementary and Secondary School*, 3(1), 70–86.
- Gapuzan, J. A. (2025). Challenges in teaching reading comprehension, fluency, and strategies to be utilized in enhancing reading comprehension. *Divine Word International Journal of Management and Humanities*, 4(4), 2354–2371.
- Garces, N. L., Delos Reyes, T. R., & Mascariñas, E. M. (2025). Improving reading comprehension of secondary Alternative Learning System (ALS) learners through the CLUES intervention program. *International Journal of Research and Innovation in Social Science*, 9(3), 6333–6344.
- Garcia, O., & Kleifgen, J. A. (2020). Translanguaging and literacies. *Reading Research Quarterly*, 55(4), 553–571.
- Hagid, M. M., & Apostol, E. P. (2024). Teaching reading strategies and challenges in the new normal: Context of a school district in Northern Luzon. *Research and Advances in Education*, 3(9), 1–13.
- LaBad, R. B., & Alindo, J. B. (2024). Perceptions of learners on reading enhancement during Catch-Up Fridays. *Ennoia Advances in Social Science, Technology and Education*, 1(1), 24–31.
- Lestari, E. Y., Suryanti, S., & Suprpto, N. (2025). Local wisdom integration in picture storybooks for elementary reading comprehension: A systematic

- literature review. *Attadrib: Jurnal Pendidikan Guru Madrasah Ibtidaiyah*, 8(3), 717–729.
- Malipot, M. H. (2024, June 18). Learners lose nearly 3 months of learning in SY 2023–2024 — study. *Manila Bulletin*. <https://mb.com.ph/2024/06/18/learners-lose-nearly-3-months-of-learning-in-sy-2023-2024-study>
- Matalines, A. M. J. (2025). Development of remediation materials: A tool to enhance reading performance of learners. *Psychology and Education: A Multidisciplinary Journal*, 37(7), 664–673.
- Mutya, R. C., Tondo Jr., R. C., Aragon, K. M. P., Tablate, D. J. C., & Bonotan, A. M. (2025). Strategic intervention materials-based instruction on disaster literacy using ADDIE model. *Frontiers in Education*, 10, 1671079. <https://doi.org/10.3389/educ.2025.1671079>
- Panklam, A., & Kaowiwattanakul, S. (2024). From globalization to localization: Promoting EFL learners' reading comprehension using GFOS model. *Theory and Practice in Language Studies*, 14(9), 2791–2801.
- Pathomchaiwat, L., & Thongrin, S. (2025). Enhancing EFL pre-service teachers' reading strategy instruction through contextualized materials. *Reflections*, 32(2), 787–812.
- PISA. (2022). *PISA 2022 results: Philippines country note*. OECD Publishing.
- Rafanan, R. J., et al. (2024). Impact of customized reading remediation on reading fluency. *International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research and Analysis*, 7(6), 1234–1245.
- Requiso-Jimenez, J. D., & Bascos-Ocampo, R. (2022). Improving reading comprehension skills of Grade 5 pupils using localized reading selections. *Asian Journal of Language, Literature and Culture Studies*, 5(4), 209–218.
- Sanico, J. M., & Gorumba, J. A. (2025). Contextualizing instruction: Addressing learning gaps through localized teaching. *Business, Education, Social Sciences, and Technology Journal*, 1(1).
- Soria, S. F. E. (2024). Reading program in the National Learning Camp. *International Journal of Research and Scientific Innovation*, 11(03), 418–435.
- Taherdoost, H. (2022). Designing a questionnaire for research. *International Journal of Academic Research in Management*, 11(1), 8–24.
- Talain, R. C., & Cruzado, A. D. (2024). Improving comprehension skills through Catch-Up Fridays intervention. *International Journal of Theory and Application in Elementary and Secondary School Education*, 6(1), 45–58.
- Torgesen, J. K. (2000). Individual differences in response to early interventions in reading. *Learning Disabilities Research & Practice*, 15(1), 55–64.

UNESCO. (2020). *Global education monitoring report 2020*. UNESCO Publishing.

UNICEF. (2021). *Foundational literacy and numeracy report*. UNICEF.

Villalva, R. (2023). A critical review of the Philippine Informal Reading Inventory (Phil-IRI). *International Journal of Research Publications*, 121(1), 208–214.

Vygotsky, L. S. (1978). *Mind in society*. Harvard University Press.

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